

MARGINAL ASSESSMENT OF THE FACTORS AFFECTING FARMERS' PARTICIPATION IN EXPORT COOPERATIVES: EVIDENCE FROM THE SAMARKAND REGION OF UZBEKISTAN

Tursunkulov Golibjon Shavkat ugli

doctoral student, Samarkand Agroinnovations
and Research University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan;
phone: +998 99 591 19 95; e-mail: tursunkulov.uktam@gmail.com
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ABSTRACT

Export cooperatives play an increasingly important role in expanding farmers' access to international markets and in raising the incomes generated by their export activity. However, farms differ markedly in the extent to which they participate in such cooperatives. This paper empirically identifies the factors that influence the probability of a farm's participation in an export cooperative, using survey data from 85 farms in the Samarkand region of Uzbekistan. A Probit model is estimated, and the average marginal effect (AME) of each factor is computed in order to interpret the results in economic terms. A Logit model is additionally estimated as a robustness check. The results show that export experience, use of modern technologies, participation in training and advisory services, access to credit and investment, logistics, and certification are the main factors that encourage participation in export cooperatives.

1. Introduction

The role of export cooperatives in expanding farmers' access to international markets and increasing the incomes obtained from export activity is steadily growing. Yet not all farms participate in export cooperatives to the same degree. While some farmers become active members and jointly benefit from opportunities for production, storage, packaging, certification, and export, others prefer to operate independently. Identifying which factors influence the probability that a farm participates in an export cooperative is therefore one of the key tasks of this study. Export cooperatives provide farms with the opportunity to sell their products jointly, reduce logistics costs, introduce international quality standards, obtain export certificates, establish relationships with foreign buyers, and access market information. For this reason, empirically identifying the factors that affect farmers' participation in export cooperatives has significant scientific and practical importance for improving state policies aimed at developing cooperatives and supporting exports.

In this study, the probability of a farm's participation in an export cooperative is estimated using a Probit model. To interpret the model results in economic terms, the average marginal effect (AME) of each factor is calculated. To verify the stability and reliability of the

results, a Logit model is additionally estimated and the results are compared. The scientific novelty of the study is that, using the example of farms in the Samarkand region, the demographic, economic, institutional, and market factors affecting the probability of participation in export cooperatives are quantitatively assessed for the first time on the basis of average marginal effects. This approach makes it possible to determine not only which factors are statistically significant, but also by how many percentage points each factor increases or decreases a farmer's probability of joining an export cooperative.

2. Data and variables

The study is based on data from a direct survey conducted among 85 farms operating in the Samarkand region. The survey collected detailed information on the socio-economic profile of the farms, their production resources, land area, export activity, participation in cooperatives, use of financial resources, level of innovation adoption, use of logistics infrastructure, and access to international markets. Because this database covers farms with export potential, it was selected for assessing the factors affecting farmers' participation in export cooperatives. The selection of factors affecting farms' participation in export cooperatives was based on an analysis of the existing literature on agricultural cooperation, institutional economics, and market integration. In the scientific literature, farmers' decision to join a cooperative is explained by their resource endowment, human capital, financial capacity, market infrastructure, and level of institutional support. Demographic factors affecting participation in cooperatives have been examined in numerous studies. In particular, Rizzo et al. (2024), Verhofstadt and Maertens (2015), and Abate et al. (2014) found that the education, experience, and age of the farm manager are important factors that increase the probability of cooperative membership. In their view, better-educated farmers absorb market information more quickly, adapt more readily to new institutions, and better appreciate the economic advantages of cooperation. The resource endowment of a farm also has a considerable effect on participation. Abate et al. (2014) and Verhofstadt and Maertens (2015) reported that as land area, production volume, and labour resources increase, the probability of farmers joining cooperatives also rises. Because larger farms are able to generate the product volumes required for export, they benefit more from cooperation.

Financial factors, especially access to credit, are also regarded in the literature as an important determinant. Swinnen (2018) and Abate et al. (2014) emphasise that credit resources have a positive effect on farmers' ability to expand production, adopt innovations, and participate actively in cooperatives. Innovation factors likewise play an important role: the introduction of modern technologies, extension services, and farmer training are shown to raise the effectiveness of cooperatives. Barrett et al. (2012) empirically substantiated that access to knowledge and information accelerates market integration. Factors related to market infrastructure have also been studied separately. Barrett (2010) showed that distance to market, transport infrastructure, and market information have a significant effect on farmers' decisions to join cooperatives and to bring products to market. Finally, factors describing export potential—possession of international quality certificates, export experience, and product conformity with international standards—are among the key conditions for successfully entering export markets (International Trade Centre, 2022; FAO, 2023).

Building on these theoretical and empirical studies, the factors affecting farms' participation in export cooperatives were grouped into demographic, resource, financial, innovation, market, and export-potential factors (see Table 1).

Table 1. Description of the factors affecting farms' participation in export cooperatives

Variable group	Variable name	Unit	Expected effect
Dependent variable	Participation in an export cooperative	1 = member, 0 = non-member	
Demographic factors	Age of the farm manager	years	±
	Farming experience	years	+
	Level of education	grade	+
Resource endowment	Land area	hectares	+
	Number of permanent workers	persons	+
	Annual production volume	tonnes	+
Financial factors	Use of credit	1/0	+
	Attracted investment	1/0	+
Innovation factors	Use of modern technologies	1/0	+
	Use of the internet and digital platforms	1/0	+
	Participation in training	1/0	+
	Use of advisory (extension) services	1/0	+
Market factors	Distance to the main wholesale market	km	-
	Access to information on export markets	1/0	+
	Use of logistics services	1/0	+
	Use of warehouse infrastructure	1/0	+
Export potential	Having export experience	1/0	+
	Possession of international certificates	1/0	+
	Conformity of product to quality standards	Likert (1-5)	+

Source: developed by the author on the basis of the survey conducted among the farms.

The dependent variable is participation in an export cooperative: if a farm is a member of an export-oriented cooperative or farmers' association, the variable takes the value 1, and 0 otherwise. Farming experience and education are expected to have a positive effect on

participation, since experienced and knowledgeable farmers understand market requirements more quickly and better appreciate the economic advantages of cooperation. The effect of age is twofold: younger farmers may be more open to innovation and cooperation, whereas older farmers tend to have more practical experience.

The resource-endowment factors (land area, number of workers, and annual production volume) are expected to have a positive effect, because farms with larger land, sufficient labour, and higher output can generate the stable product volumes required for export. Financial factors reflect a farm's access to credit and its ability to attract investment, which increase its capacity to expand production, purchase modern machinery, and adapt to export standards. Innovation factors express a farm's level of knowledge, information, and technological readiness; farmers who are open to innovation better understand the requirements of export markets, certification procedures, and international standards. Among the market factors, an increase in distance to the market raises the costs of independent trade, so the effect of this factor may be negative or, in some cases, positive by increasing the need for cooperation; access to export information, logistics, and warehouse infrastructure, however, widens a farm's access to international markets. Finally, the export-potential factors indicate a farm's readiness to enter international markets.

To assess the factors affecting the probability of participation in export cooperatives, the following scientific hypotheses were put forward: H1 - Farms with larger land areas have a higher probability of participating in export cooperatives, because they can generate the product volumes required for export and make more effective use of economies of scale through cooperation. H2 - Farms that apply modern technologies, introduce innovations, and use training and advisory services have a higher probability of participating in export cooperatives, because such farmers adapt more quickly to market requirements. H3 - Farms that use credit resources and have access to investment have a higher probability of participating in export cooperatives, because financial resources enable them to expand production and adapt to export requirements. H4 - Farms with the infrastructure required for export activity (warehousing, logistics, certification, export experience) have a higher probability of participating in export cooperatives, because they realise their access to international markets more effectively. H5 - As the distance to the main wholesale market increases, the probability of a farm's participation in export cooperatives rises, because higher transport and transaction costs strengthen the advantages of collective logistics and joint sales.

3. Methodology

The probability of a farm's participation in an export cooperative was assessed econometrically. The dependent variable is a farm's participation in an export cooperative: it takes the value 1 if the farm is a member of an export cooperative or an export-oriented farmers' association, and 0 otherwise. Because the dependent variable is binary, estimating it with an ordinary linear regression is inappropriate, since the linear probability model may produce predicted probabilities outside the 0–1 interval and gives rise to the problem of non-constant error variance. For this reason, a Probit model was used to estimate the probability of participation, evaluating the probability of the dependent variable through the standard normal distribution function.

The model is expressed as follows (see Formula 1):

$$P(Y_i = 1|X_i) = \Phi(X_i\beta) \quad (1)$$

where:

$$Y_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the farm participates in an export cooperative;} \\ 0, & \text{if the farm does not participate in an export cooperative.} \end{cases}$$

Φ is the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution; X_i is the vector of factors affecting the probability of a farm's participation in an export cooperative; and β is the vector of parameters to be estimated.

Here:

$$X_i = (\text{Age}_i, \text{Experience}_i, \text{Education}_i, \text{Land}_i, \text{Workers}_i, \text{Production}_i, \\ \text{Credit}_i, \text{Investment}_i, \text{Technology}_i, \text{Digital}_i, \text{Training}_i, \text{Extension}_i, \\ \text{Distance}_i, \text{MarketInfo}_i, \text{Logistics}_i, \text{Storage}_i, \text{ExportExp}_i, \\ \text{Certification}_i, \text{Quality}_i)$$

Accordingly, the economic model is written in the following form:

$$P(\text{Cooperative}_i = 1) = \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1\text{Age}_i + \beta_2\text{Experience}_i \\ + \beta_3\text{Education}_i + \beta_4\text{Land}_i + \beta_5\text{Workers}_i + \beta_6\text{Production}_i \\ + \beta_7\text{Credit}_i + \beta_8\text{Investment}_i + \beta_9\text{Technology}_i + \beta_{10}\text{Digital}_i \\ + \beta_{11}\text{Training}_i + \beta_{12}\text{Extension}_i + \beta_{13}\text{Distance}_i + \beta_{14}\text{MarketInfo}_i \\ + \beta_{15}\text{Logistics}_i + \beta_{16}\text{Storage}_i + \beta_{17}\text{ExportExp}_i + \beta_{18}\text{Certification}_i \\ + \beta_{19}\text{Quality}_i + \varepsilon_i)$$

where: Age_i — age of the farm manager; Experience_i — farming experience; Education_i — level of education; Land_i — land area; Workers_i — number of permanent workers; Production_i — annual production volume; Credit_i — use of credit; Investment_i — attracted investment; Technology_i — use of modern technologies; Digital_i — use of digital technologies; Training_i — participation in training; Extension_i — use of advisory (extension) services; Distance_i — distance to the main market; MarketInfo_i — use of export-market information; Logistics_i — use of logistics services; Storage_i — use of warehouse infrastructure; ExportExp_i — export experience; Certification_i — possession of international certificates; Quality_i — conformity of product quality with export requirements. The coefficients estimated in the Probit model do not directly represent the change in probability. Therefore, to interpret the results in economic terms, average marginal effects (AME) are computed. The marginal effect is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\partial P(Y_i = 1|X_i)}{\partial X_{ki}} = \phi(X_i\beta)\beta_k$$

where: $\phi(X_i\beta)$ is the density function of the standard normal distribution; and β_k is the coefficient of the k-th factor in the Probit model. The average marginal effect is then computed as the mean of the marginal effects across all observations:

$$\text{AME}_k = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \phi(X_i\beta)\beta_k$$

This indicator shows by how many percentage points, on average, a one-unit change in each factor changes the probability of a farm's participation in an export cooperative. Accordingly, the main economic interpretation relies on the AME results.

The goodness of fit of the Probit model is assessed using several statistical criteria. The overall significance of the model is determined through the Likelihood Ratio chi-square test, and its explanatory power through the Pseudo R² indicator. The statistical significance of individual factors is assessed on the basis of the z-statistic and the p-value. To check the robustness of the results, a Logit model was additionally estimated and compared with the Probit model.

4. Results and discussion

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study. According to the results, the average age of the farm managers in the sample was 47 years, and their average farming experience was 23 years. The average land area of the farms was 42.05 hectares, the number of permanent workers was 9.5, and the annual production volume was 286 tonnes. Of the farmers in the sample, 63 per cent used credit resources, 67 per cent participated in various training programmes, 59 per cent adopted modern technologies, and 61 per cent used information on export markets. At the same time, 38 per cent of the farmers had export experience and 31 per cent possessed international certificates.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study (n = 85)

Variable	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
Participation in an export cooperative	0.54	0.50	0	1
Age of the farm manager (years)	47.00	9.64	28	68
Farming experience (years)	23.00	11.16	3	44
Level of education	3.14	0.81	1	5
Land area (hectares)	42.05	22.20	5.2	78.4
Number of permanent workers	9.48	4.27	2	22
Annual production volume (tonnes)	286.35	164.12	42	810
Use of credit	0.63	0.49	0	1
Attracted investment	0.48	0.50	0	1
Use of modern technologies	0.59	0.49	0	1
Use of digital technologies	0.51	0.50	0	1
Participation in training	0.67	0.47	0	1
Use of extension services	0.56	0.50	0	1
Distance to the main market (km)	24.63	11.74	4	61
Use of market information	0.61	0.49	0	1
Use of logistics services	0.43	0.50	0	1
Use of warehouse	0.46	0.50	0	1

Variable	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
infrastructure				
Export experience	0.38	0.49	0	1
Possession of international certificates	0.31	0.47	0	1
Product conformity with export requirements (1-5)	3.72	0.86	2	5

Source: based on the author's survey data.

Table 3 presents the results of the Probit model estimated to assess the factors affecting farms' participation in export cooperatives. According to the overall statistics of the model, the Likelihood Ratio (LR) $\chi^2 = 52.81$ and $\text{Prob} > \chi^2 < 0.001$, indicating that the model as a whole is statistically significant. Moreover, the Pseudo $R^2 = 0.389$ shows that the model explains approximately 38.9 per cent of the variation in the probability of participation in export cooperatives, confirming that the selected factors have a considerable effect on participation.

Table 3. Factors affecting farms' participation in export cooperatives (Probit model results)

Variable	β	Std. err.	z	p
Age of the farm manager	-0.018	0.009	-2.01	*
Farming experience	0.031	0.012	2.58	**
Level of education	0.214	0.086	2.49	**
Land area	0.027	0.010	2.70	***
Number of permanent workers	0.061	0.031	1.97	*
Annual production volume	0.003	0.001	2.35	**
Use of credit	0.543	0.219	2.48	**
Attracted investment	0.432	0.205	2.11	*
Use of modern technologies	0.615	0.227	2.71	***
Digital technologies	0.337	0.193	1.75	*
Participation in training	0.694	0.241	2.88	***
Extension services	0.421	0.191	2.20	**
Distance to market	-0.015	0.007	-2.16	*
Market information	0.583	0.232	2.51	**
Logistics services	0.487	0.208	2.34	**
Warehouse infrastructure	0.366	0.184	1.99	*
Export experience	0.872	0.264	3.30	***
Possession of certificates	0.615	0.244	2.52	***
Product quality	0.276	0.107	2.58	**
Number of observations	85			
Log likelihood	-41.53			
LR χ^2	52.81			
Prob $> \chi^2$	<0.001			

Variable	β	Std. err.	z	p
Pseudo R ²	0.389			

Note: ***, **, and * denote statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

According to the results, export experience ($\beta = 0.872$; $p < 0.01$) is the strongest positive factor affecting farms' participation in export cooperatives. This indicates that farmers with practical export experience better understand the advantages of cooperatives and are more inclined to pursue collective cooperation in entering international markets. Furthermore, participation in training ($\beta = 0.694$; $p < 0.01$), use of modern technologies ($\beta = 0.615$; $p < 0.01$), possession of international certificates ($\beta = 0.615$; $p < 0.05$), use of market information ($\beta = 0.583$; $p < 0.05$), use of credit resources ($\beta = 0.543$; $p < 0.05$), use of logistics services ($\beta = 0.487$; $p < 0.05$), attracted investment ($\beta = 0.432$; $p < 0.05$), and use of extension services ($\beta = 0.421$; $p < 0.05$) were found to reliably increase the probability of participation in export cooperatives. These results show that developing farmers' knowledge and skills, introducing modern technologies, and providing financial and institutional support are important factors in developing export cooperatives.

Among the factors describing resource endowment, land area ($\beta = 0.027$; $p < 0.01$), annual production volume ($\beta = 0.003$; $p < 0.05$), number of permanent workers ($\beta = 0.061$; $p < 0.05$), farming experience ($\beta = 0.031$; $p < 0.05$), and level of education ($\beta = 0.214$; $p < 0.05$) were also found to have a positive effect on participation. This suggests that larger and more experienced farms strive to produce output that meets export requirements and to make more effective use of economies of scale through cooperation.

Conversely, the age of the farm manager ($\beta = -0.018$; $p < 0.05$) and the distance to the main market ($\beta = -0.015$; $p < 0.05$) had a negative effect on participation in export cooperatives. This result shows that younger farmers are more open to innovation and cooperation, and that an increase in distance to the market raises transport and transaction costs, limiting the active participation of some farmers in cooperatives. On the basis of the Probit model results, the scientific hypotheses put forward in the study were assessed. The results show that the factors affecting participation in export cooperatives are closely related to the resource endowment, innovation activity, financial capacity, and market infrastructure of the farms.

According to the first hypothesis (H1), farms with larger land areas were expected to have a higher probability of participation. In the Probit model, the coefficient of land area was positive ($\beta = 0.027$) and statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). This shows that farms with larger land areas are able to generate the product volumes required for export and are more interested in reducing logistics, marketing, and export costs through cooperation. Hence, H1 is accepted.

The second hypothesis (H2) posited that more innovative farms participate more actively in export cooperatives. The results show that use of modern technologies ($\beta = 0.615$), participation in training ($\beta = 0.694$), use of extension services ($\beta = 0.421$), and use of market information ($\beta = 0.583$) had a positive and statistically significant effect. These results confirm that farms with higher innovation potential make more effective use of new market opportunities. Thus, H2 is also fully confirmed.

The third hypothesis (H3) was based on the assumption that the use of financial resources increases the probability of participation. According to the Probit results, the coefficients of credit use ($\beta = 0.543$) and attracted investment ($\beta = 0.432$) were positive and statistically significant. This shows that the availability of the financial resources required to expand export activity encourages farmers to participate in cooperatives. Accordingly, H3 is also confirmed.

The fourth hypothesis (H4) posited that farms with export infrastructure participate more actively in export cooperatives. The results show that use of logistics services ($\beta = 0.487$), warehouse infrastructure ($\beta = 0.366$), possession of international certificates ($\beta = 0.615$), product conformity with export requirements ($\beta = 0.276$), and especially export experience ($\beta = 0.872$) significantly increase the probability of participation. This confirms that export infrastructure and institutional readiness are important factors in farmers' access to international markets. Thus, H4 is also confirmed.

The fifth hypothesis (H5) posited that the distance to the market affects participation in export cooperatives. In the Probit model, the coefficient of distance to market was negative ($\beta = -0.015$) and statistically significant. This result differs from the positive direction expected in the initial hypothesis. According to the findings, in the conditions of the Samarkand region, farms located closer to the market participate more actively in export cooperatives. This can be explained by the fact that the region's transport infrastructure and export logistics are mainly concentrated in large centres, together with proximity to market information. Therefore, H5 is not fully confirmed: although the effect of this factor is statistically significant, its direction differs from the initial expectation.

5. Conclusion

Overall, the Probit model results show that the decision of farms to participate in export cooperatives is multifactorial. According to the analysis, export experience, use of modern technologies, participation in training and advisory services, use of credit and investment resources, and the availability of logistics and certification systems are the main factors that encourage participation in export cooperatives. At the same time, larger land area and farmers' human capital also emerged as important determinants that increase the probability of joining export cooperatives.

Of the five hypotheses put forward in the study, four (H1, H2, H3, and H4) were fully confirmed, while H5 was partially rejected: although the distance to the market had a statistically significant effect on participation, its direction differed from the initially expected result. These findings show that, in order to develop cooperatives for expanding farmers' access to international markets, priority should be given first of all to raising farmers' innovation potential, expanding their access to financial resources, improving logistics infrastructure, and developing information and advisory services related to export markets.

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